

Application of Donabedian Quality-of-Care Framework to Assess the Outcomes of Medication Use in Pediatric ICU: A Review

Ali Mohammed Alhassan ¹, Zahra Hussain Alsalamah¹, Sawsan Hussain Alsalamah², Maryam Nasser Alabdullah³, Sukinah Hussain Alobaid¹, Fatimah Abdullah Alnwaiser⁴, Ahlam Abdulwahab Albeladi¹, Enbihar Abdulwahab Albeladi⁵, Ahmed Taher Albinmaan⁶, Fatima Abdullah Al Bindeera¹, Fatimah Saleh Alghanem⁷, Habib Hussien Almusharaf¹, Ibrahim Ahmed Alsaleem⁸, Ibrahim Abdullah Alhajji ⁹, Emad Taj Alshakhs ¹⁰

1. Al Faisal PHC
2. Prince Saud Bin Jalawy hospital
3. Mahasen PHC
4. Maternity and Children's Hospital
5. Alomran Hospital
6. Aloyon PHC
7. Al-Omran General Hospital
8. King Fahad Hospital
9. Compliance Department
10. Compliance Department

ABSTRACT

The Donabedian quality-of-care framework offers a structured approach to evaluating healthcare quality, encompassing structure, process, and outcome domains. Medication use in the pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) requires special attention due to the high-risk environment and vulnerable population. This review explores the application of the Donabedian framework in assessing medication use in the PICU, focusing on structural factors such as staffing and technology, processes such as prescribing and administration, and outcomes such as adverse drug events and clinical efficacy. Recommendations for improving quality and patient safety are discussed.

Introduction

The pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) is a complex and dynamic healthcare setting where patients often require intricate and high-risk medication regimens. Medication errors and adverse drug events (ADEs) remain significant concerns, given the vulnerable population and the potential for severe outcomes(1,2).The Donabedian quality-of-care framework—developed by Avedis Donabedian—provides a comprehensive method for evaluating healthcare systems by analyzing three interrelated components: structure, process, and outcomes(3). Applying this framework to medication use in the PICU can help identify gaps in care quality, optimize medication management, and improve patient outcomes.

Overview of the Donabedian Framework

❖ Structure

Structure refers to the physical and organizational infrastructure in which care is delivered. In the context of PICU medication use, this includes:

- Staffing levels and expertise (e.g., availability of pediatric pharmacists)
- Technology (e.g., electronic health records [EHRs], automated dispensing systems)
- Policies and protocols for medication safety(4)

❖ Process

Process encompasses the actions taken to deliver care. In the PICU, this includes:

- Prescribing practices (e.g., dose adjustments for pediatric patients)
- Medication administration (e.g., adherence to guidelines, double-checks)
- Monitoring for adverse drug reactions and therapeutic effectiveness (5)

❖ Outcomes

Outcomes represent the results of care delivery, such as:

- Reduction in ADEs
- Improvement in clinical outcomes (e.g., resolution of infection, stabilization of vital signs)
- Patient and family satisfaction with care(6,7)

Application of the Donabedian Framework in the PICU

Structure Domain

The structural elements of PICU medication use significantly influence care quality:

- **Staffing:** The presence of dedicated pediatric pharmacists reduces medication errors by 27% compared to units without such specialized support(7).
- **Technology:** Integration of computerized physician order entry (CPOE) systems has shown a 55% reduction in prescription errors in pediatric settings (8).
- **Environment:** Standardized medication storage and labeling practices help prevent administration errors.

Process Domain

The medication use process in the PICU involves several steps, each of which presents opportunities for error or improvement:

- **Prescribing:** Pediatric patients require weight-based dosing, which increases the complexity and potential for error. Clinical decision support systems (CDSS) embedded in EHRs have improved dosing accuracy(9).
- **Administration:** Double-checking protocols and the use of barcoded medication administration (BCMA) systems significantly reduce wrong-patient and wrong-dose errors(10).
- **Monitoring:** Continuous monitoring of therapeutic effects and adverse reactions is critical. Programs that engage families in identifying early signs of ADEs have shown promise(11).

Outcome Domain

Evaluating outcomes helps determine the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving medication use:

- **Adverse Drug Events (ADEs):** Studies have reported a 30% reduction in ADEs in PICUs with robust medication safety protocols(12).

- **Clinical Efficacy:** Effective medication management has been associated with shorter PICU stays and reduced mortality rates.
- **Family Satisfaction:** Families report higher satisfaction levels when clear communication about medication safety and efficacy is provided.

Challenges in Applying the Donabedian Framework

- **Data Availability:** Comprehensive data collection for structure, process, and outcome metrics can be challenging in busy PICU settings.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Effective medication management requires coordination among physicians, nurses, and pharmacists, which can be hindered by communication barriers.
- **Technology Integration:** While tools like CPOE and BCMA systems improve safety, their implementation is often costly and resource-intensive.

Strategies for Improvement

- **Enhancing Structural Support:**
 - Employ pediatric pharmacists in all PICUs.
 - Ensure availability of advanced technologies like BCMA systems.
 - Develop standardized protocols for high-risk medications.
- **Optimizing Processes:**
 - Conduct regular training sessions for PICU staff on medication safety.
 - Implement multidisciplinary rounds focusing on medication management.
 - Engage families in the care process to identify potential errors early.
- **Monitoring Outcomes:**
 - Use real-time analytics to track ADEs and medication errors.
 - Conduct periodic surveys to assess family satisfaction.
 - Benchmark outcomes against national or international standards.

Future Directions

- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** AI-driven predictive analytics can identify high-risk patients and optimize medication regimens in real-time.

- **Patient-Centered Approaches:** Greater emphasis on involving families in medication management.
- **Global Standards:** Developing universally applicable guidelines for medication safety in pediatric ICUs.

Conclusion

The Donabedian framework offers a valuable lens through which to evaluate and improve medication use in the PICU. By addressing structural deficiencies, optimizing processes, and focusing on outcomes, healthcare providers can enhance the safety and quality of care delivered to critically ill children. Future advancements in technology and interdisciplinary collaboration will further strengthen medication management strategies in these high-stakes environments.

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